

The Analysis of Parenting Patterns in Instilling Morals of Early Childhood

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the parenting style of parents in instilling morals in children from an early age. The research method used is a qualitative and descriptive analysis approach. Observation, interviews, and questionnaires were used to collect data. And data analysis techniques such as data reduction, presentation, and conclusion drawing. The results found indicate that there is a diversity of parenting styles carried out by student parents in instilling morals in children from an early age; among these parenting styles are democratic, permissive, and authoritarian parenting styles. The democratic parenting pattern shows the greatest level of acceptance compared to the permissive and authoritarian types. So, it can be concluded that, based on the existing research data, parents have a tendency to instill morals at an early age by using democratic parenting.

Keywords: *Moral Parenting, Parenting Parents, Early Childhood*

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INTRODUCTION

Education is an activity that cannot be separated from human life. Because humans were born on earth, Allah has bestowed a mind on them that makes them more noble than the creatures He created. With this glory, humans serve as caliphs on this earth. Educating is work that never ends. Education means passing on virtues, wisdom, skills, inspiration, and ideological provisions that are grounded in the direction of divine guidance (Ferdian Utama, 2017). Educating is a field of unlimited dedication. Educating is one step to prepare a better generation for the future (Abdullah, 2007).

The family consists of parents, namely the father and mother, and also other family members. Parents hold the learner principle as proffered by Ki Hajar Dewantara that, "Everyone is a teacher and every place is a school." Of course, we agree that space and time are not reasons that limit the rolling of values (Permatasari, Keguruan, & Pendidikan, 2021). The role of both parent and teacher, or vice versa, is like two sides of a coin that are inseparable. It is permanently attached to every human being (Zebua & Sunarti, 2020). The unification of the predicate of parents and teachers is the destiny of humans as chosen beings (Ramli et al., 2023). It is human nature that the flow of time leads us all towards the momentum of fulfilling our mandate as mothers or fathers. This means that a human being must be ready to play a role as an educational practitioner. At least for his own children (Amini, 1981).

Because both parents and the child must be teachers for their child when he is born. The obligation to teach children about various things in life cannot be left entirely to other people or educational institutions. Before children can attend school, they must complete a learning process at home (Setiawan et al., 2021). There is important advice for parents from Dr. Muhammad Muhammad Badri in his book, *Soul Touch for Our Children*. Love your children with real love; point out their faults gently and politely; be patient with their behavior; act occasionally as though you are ignoring their faults; set yourself as an example to them; and use the proper ways and methods in doing so. Use the language of love and affection (Astuti et al., 2023).

Based on what was said by Dr. Muhammad Muhammad Badri above, it was emphasized that a home for children must be created as comfortably as possible with the right parenting style: loving children in a real way, correcting mistakes gently and politely, and controlling oneself so that they are able to deal with various mistakes in children's behavior while correcting them in the right way (Badri, 2011). The role of parents in parenting their children becomes very important for children, so that the example of good and positive actions carried out by parents is a disciplinary process from an early age; otherwise, mental depression, psychological pressure, stress, and mental suffering often occur among parents (Panji et al., 2023). It is the role of parents to provide a strong foundation and handle the child from an early age (Hafizh, 1997). When the world of education outside the home environment, such as schools and others,

has various things that he can absorb without any positive or negative considerations, it is the role of parents, who are the main guides for children, to provide exemplary education as the main provision to become a generation of morals that is ready to face the challenges of the times (Majid, 2012).

The current generation is that of the twenty-first century, which is currently rushing along with the flow of globalization. Globalization is a process of worldwide social order that knows no boundaries (Nugroho et al., 2023). With this globalization, there has been a shift in behavior patterns caused by the globalization of information and communication; in fact, it has involved many fields, including patterns of behavior in the family environment, at school, and in people's lives. From this we can see how behavior patterns change in the relationship between teachers and students, the relationship between parents and their children, and the community-neighborhood relationship between individuals (Parinussa et al., 2023). The globalization of information and communication has an effect on lifestyles, both positively and negatively (Sukmawati, 2009). Globalization has a negative impact on society, as ordinary people tend to live a luxurious lifestyle. By watching soap operas and telenovelas on TV, people cannot adjust to their household income.

Many things have an impact on the flow of globalization that we have observed as the example above. There are positives as well as negatives (Sukmawati, 2022). All of these things can certainly affect the child's soul if not given sufficient supervision by parents. What's more, nowadays, gadgets are items that almost everyone in this world uses, including toddlers. Everyone cannot miss this one thing. If, since toddlers' parents easily provide free access to children to be able to feel the developments that are happening in this world, it becomes an inevitable habit if he grows up, this must be balanced with parental supervision and providing a genuine role model. So as not to cause negativity (Susanto, 2019).

According to Bambang Tri, Goleman's theory of emotional intelligence (EQ) should help us understand why good morals are such an important part of life (Permatasari, Keguruan, & Pendidikan, 2021). With the flood of information, the increasing number of people, and the increasingly complicated complexity of life, many people are infected with liver disease, aka low emotional intelligence (Utama, 2018). In developmental psychology theory, the early age of children (0-6 years) is the golden age for the development of their intellectual and emotional intelligence. The child has the opportunity to be formed with noble character at this stage after birth, in accordance with the active role of the father and mother (Tri, 2012).

METHODOLOGY

The method used in writing this thesis is the descriptive method. Respondents in this study were the guardians of Tk Bakti Nusa Indah students, totaling 22 people. Collecting data in this study is through observation, interviews, questionnaires, and data analysis. After the data is collected, the steps taken by the next writer are to process the data, so that the data can be analyzed and conclusions drawn. In the

process of analyzing data on the main components, it must be understood in depth. These components are data collection, data reduction, data review, and drawing conclusions or verification. To analyze various existing data, the analytic-descriptive method was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The total number of respondents was 16 people, all of them were women. Mothers of Bakti Nusa Indah Kindergarten students, in particular. This is in accordance with what researchers see in the field that the activities of delivering, waiting, and picking up children are carried out by mothers. There were two respondents aged 25-30 years, twelve respondents aged 31-35 years, and two respondents aged 35-40 years. The last education of the majority of respondents was senior high school (SMA), namely 7 people, 3 of whom graduated from elementary school (SD). 3 junior high school graduates, 1 diploma (D3) graduate, and 2 undergraduate graduates. The majority of respondents work as housewives, namely 10 people; the rest work as private employees, 6 people. Only 16 people were able to respond to this research based on the data after processing.

In accordance with the results of interviews with several parents of researchers, that they give children freedom of expression and action so that children can grow and develop confidently. However, this is still accompanied by parental supervision so that when something goes wrong, parents provide direction with good communication. Researchers also interviewed parents, who stated that it was an obligation for parents to prepare everything needed by their children. The majority of the parents who responded agreed that parents should provide understanding guidance to their children. In accordance with what the researchers observed when recess arrived, some parents gave advice and directions to children with great affection, and when something happened in class, parents gave soothing explanations and advice so that children understood easily.

Most parents pay attention and choose good friends for their children. According to Ananda Reza's parents, "I free my child to be friends with anyone, but it is still under my monitoring, for example, when he plays with his friends at home, I monitor from afar, if his friend Kiran is not good in terms of attitude and words, I will remind Kiran not to imitate his friends, and try to be friends with others." Because I believe that making friends has a significant impact on Kiran." According to what researchers observed in the field, parents are attempting to teach their children that there are some snacks that can be purchased and others that cannot, by using language that children can understand so that children understand what is allowed and what is not.

From the results of the interviews, parents also said that being fair is an important thing that must be applied in the family so that children get attention, affection, and fair treatment so as not to cause jealousy between brothers and sisters. almost all parents agree to spend time by inviting their children to recreation areas. From research in the field, some parents, fathers, and mothers work so that children are entrusted to grandmothers, maids, or neighbors. Meet

only when coming home from work and when dropping the kids off at school. This causes children to play without sufficient supervision from their parents, so that parents do not know too much about their children's daily activities. Parents said they only knew who their children were playing with and when without providing sufficient supervision because work routines took up quite a bit of their time. Some of these things conclude that most parents still let their children play without sufficient supervision, due to their busy work.

According to the findings of the interviews, parents today would be very risky if they gave their children complete freedom without exercising any control, because it would affect all of their children's words and attitudes, especially morals, because children were influenced by their environment outside the home, which was significant. The results of interviews with several parents, all working parents, stated that children are given freedom because parents really cannot supervise enough. Parents' time is up at the office, and when they are at home, they can only supervise when the child is at home, not when they are playing. Other parents stated that they did not agree with this because early childhood really needed parental supervision. Early childhood children, according to their parents, like to imitate what they see around them. So, I really don't agree with letting children just do something without parental supervision. From the results of interviews, parents stated that warning when a child is wrong is the obligation of parents in educating children so that good morals are instilled in them, not the best thing. If you don't remind them, they won't know whether what they are doing is the right thing or the wrong thing. Can be fatal if left until he grows up. Children can have bad morals in the future.

Researchers also discovered that most parents are sensitive to their children's needs; for example, if there are problems in class, parents invite their children to communicate and solve problems together. According to research in the field, some parents force their children to obey orders, such as not being able to eat more than they should, having snacks according to what their mother allows, not playing in the dirt, not playing during nap time, and so on. From the results of interviews, several parents argue that all the rules given to children are of course for the good of the child, such as having to take a nap before playing, going home according to the set time when playing, not eating snacks carelessly, and not being allowed to fight with younger siblings. These things are the teaching of goodness that must be obeyed and should not be denied by children.

In accordance with the results of an interview with Mama Kal, she said: "I want my child to develop according to his age; going forward, it's up to him what he wants to be; my job as a parent is only to direct; when what he aspires to be is good, God willing, I will always support him; but still, I always give encouragement, encouragement, and advice if he is wrong or wrong." According to the findings of the interviews, parents believe that orders and prohibitions are important because they are forms of upbringing or directions from parents to children. So that children understand what is permissible and what is not permissible, what is good and what is not good, what is legal and what is illegal. Parents can't just let it go, because it is their obligation as parents.

The results of the interviews confirmed that the purpose of parents is to

punish children when they make mistakes so that children do not repeat these mistakes. almost all parents choose to practice democratic parenting. However, some parents use two types of parenting at once, namely democratic and authoritarian. This is in accordance with the results of the table above that a small number still apply authoritarian parenting in a number of circumstances which according to parents are still very necessary applied to children especially in terms of orders and prohibitions regarding good and bad. In the permissive parenting style, very few respondents answered agree, in fact, almost all of them answered disagree with this parenting style.

Researchers found that some parents still ignore the importance of choosing the right parenting style, especially in instilling morals in children from an early age. The parenting style chosen or implemented by parents is mostly democratic parenting in accordance with what is recommended by Islamic teachings that parents try to be fair to their children in the form of attention, guidance, and affection so that children feel perfect comfort and happiness. This is something good for the further development of children. This is supported by the findings of interviews with student parents, who tend to practice democratic parenting. Because this parenting style is balanced, children must be given enough love and attention. This affection and attention parents give comes in the form of communication between parents and children; with this communication, parents provide guidance and direction to children and give freedom to children to choose and do things with full responsibility so that children grow and develop confidently while still under sufficient supervision from parents.

In addition, this democratic parenting style is well suited for instilling morals in children from an early age. This is in accordance with the results of interviews with researchers: according to parents, morals are very important for a person's life, and parents really hope that their children have good morals, especially their morals towards parents. The urgency of cultivating these morals makes parents choose democratic parenting because in early childhood, children are still very easy to shape, of course with guidance full of love and affection, but there are bound to be obstacles in every process of its implementation. Apart from democratic parenting, the most common parenting dimension is authoritarian parenting. The researcher concluded that some people, in practice, apply both of these parenting styles.

Parents do not give freedom to children when doing something because parents are worried about their young children. Parents also give orders and prohibitions and give punishment if their children make mistakes. This is because parents want their children to understand that in life there are good things to do and bad things to do. And punishing children teaches them that there will be consequences for every mistake they make. According to the findings of the researcher's interviews with parents, parents who use this parenting style believe that children cannot be allowed to do anything like that; they require a firm attitude from parents in order for children to grow disciplined and for children to understand that what parents give them is good for them. child. Viewed from the perspective of implementing religious education in the family, this parenting style is more appropriate for emphasizing matters of faith and activating worship for the child. Likewise, parents must be able to instill in their children the belief that the truest

religion is a religion that worships Allah. Also, in terms of worship establish prayer.

However, the wrong application of authoritarian parenting, which is applied to children excessively, will have an uncomfortable effect on a child at an early age. Children in their early childhood want to feel comfortable and safe around their parents and family. They also want to be independent and to be treated fairly, and they want to be given opportunities to learn on their own, how to deal with problems, and demonstrate their abilities. Parents who apply excessive authoritarian parenting will overestimate the child's nature, so that parents give too many orders, prohibitions, advice, and even punishment without listening to and seeing what the child wants to convey. Parents then hope that the child is what he wants. The child will see and pay attention to the parents' attitude in detail so that he will imitate what they do. When parents give orders and prohibitions but they don't set an example, children will question and ignore parental orders. Whereas the best moral education for a child is direct parental example, rather than orders, advice, and punishment.

Despite the findings of field research and questionnaires, permissive parenting was still practiced by parents. In instilling morals, this should not be applied to children, especially in early childhood. Currently, all information can be received easily and quickly, and without sufficient supervision by parents, information and everything that children get from the environment outside the family will affect all children's behavior quickly. Parents are not sensitive to things that have a negative impact on children; bad morals can be instilled in children, and if parents' awareness of this is slow, it will inevitably result in children with bad morals in their future lives. As the researchers observed, some parents did not provide sufficient supervision when children played gadgets, especially watching YouTube. Unwanted events can occur if the child is not adequately supervised.

In addition, this permissive parenting style is based on busy parents. Parents feel tired with all their work activities, so little time is given to provide guidance and supervision of children. Some children are entrusted to their grandmothers while their parents are working, and some are cared for by babysitters. If this permissive parenting style is applied, it will have bad consequences for the child. Children will be far from religious and have bad morals because they feel they are free to do something without being noticed by their parents. During their early childhood, they will imitate more what they see in their surroundings than what they hear from those closest to them, especially their parents.

Based on the results of observations and interviews with parents, the efforts that have been given by parents in instilling morals in children from an early age are: first, introducing the Al-Quran from an early age. Al-Quran is the word of God which is a guide as well as instructions for His servants. Parents certainly want their children to be better than them. Efforts made by parents are to introduce the Koran from an early age, namely by inviting children to recite the Koran, introducing hijaiyah letters, sending children to the nearest recitation or TPA, and some are reciting the recitation every evening at Maghrib with their parents. the second: make it a habit to say thank you, apologize, and please. Based on the results of interviews parents accustom children to say thank you, sorry and please. According to parents, these three words are habits that must be ingrained from childhood so that children have good manners towards others. third, do not speak harshly. Based on

observations and interviews with parents of students, when playing, parents watch from a distance. and giving advice, and there are also parents who give direct examples of why saying harsh or bad words is not allowed.

CONCLUSION

Most parents apply democratic parenting, a small number apply authoritarian parenting, and very few apply permissive parenting; a small number apply two parenting styles at once. The choice between these two parenting styles is based on the fact that to instill morals in children, you need a parenting style that provides firmness in giving direction and guidance, but the application of this authoritarian style is not excessive and dominating. Parents still need to increase their efforts in instilling morals in children from an early age. Parents need to realize that to instill morals in children, many things can be done and applied. The age of a young child is his golden age for absorbing what he sees and hears. Parents must understand that it is up to him to set a good example for his child, so that everything he sees and hears is kindness that he will imitate and instill in himself.

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